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1 # Reproducible analyses and figures for the paddy conversion manuscript
2 # Purpose: reproduce manuscript analyses and data-driven figures from Raw data.xlsx.
3 # Input: ../Raw data.xlsx
4 # Output: output_figures/ and output_tables/
5
6 options(stringsAsFactors = FALSE, warn = 1)
7
8 required_packages <- c(
9   "readxl", "dplyr", "tidyr", "ggplot2", "patchwork", "ggdist",
10  "ggalluvial", "ggrepel", "igraph", "svglite", "ragg", "systemfonts",
11  "emmeans", "multcomp", "broom", "readr", "tibble", "purrr", "scales"
12 )
13
14 missing_packages <- required_packages[
15   !vapply(required_packages, requireNamespace, logical(1), quietly = TRUE)
16 ]
17 if (length(missing_packages)) {
18   stop(
19     "Missing required R package(s): ", paste(missing_packages, collapse = ", "),
20     "\nInstall them, then rerun this script. Packages are not installed automatically."
21   )
22 }
23 suppressPackageStartupMessages(invisible(lapply(required_packages, library, character.only = TRUE)))
24
25 this_file <- function() {
26   args <- commandArgs(trailingOnly = FALSE)
27   hit <- sub("^--file=", "", args[grepl("^--file=", args)])
28   if (length(hit)) return(normalizePath(hit[1], mustWork = FALSE))
29   if (!is.null(sys.frames()[[1]]$ofile)) return(normalizePath(sys.frames()[[1]]$ofile, mustWork = FALSE))
30   normalizePath(file.path(getwd(), "reproducible_analysis_and_figures_public.R"), mustWork = FALSE)
31 }
32
33 script_dir <- dirname(this_file())
34 if (!dir.exists(script_dir)) script_dir <- getwd()
35 setwd(script_dir)
36 raw_xlsx <- file.path("../", "Raw data.xlsx")
37 if (!file.exists(raw_xlsx)) stop("Place Raw data.xlsx in the parent directory of this script.")
38
39 output_figures <- "output_figures"
40 output_tables <- "output_tables"
41 dir.create(output_figures, recursive = TRUE, showWarnings = FALSE)
42 dir.create(output_tables, recursive = TRUE, showWarnings = FALSE)
43
44 arial_match <- try(systemfonts::match_fonts("Arial"), silent = TRUE)
45 if (!inherits(arial_match, "try-error") && nrow(arial_match) > 0 && file.exists(arial_match$path[1])) {
46   try(systemfonts::register_font("Arial", plain = arial_match$path[1]), silent = TRUE)
47 }
48
49 LAND_LEVELS <- c("WL", "DL", "GL", "IPF", "OPF")
50 SITE_LEVELS <- c(
51   "WL-1", "WL-2", "DL-1", "DL-2", "GL-1", "GL-2",
52   "IPF-1", "IPF-3", "IPF-5", "IPF-10", "IPF-15",
53   "OPF-1", "OPF-3", "OPF-5", "OPF-10", "OPF-15"
54 )
55 LAND_COLORS <- c(WL = "#6B6B6B", DL = "#E69F00", GL = "#009E73", IPF = "#0072B2", OPF = "#CC79A7")
56 LAND_SHAPES <- c(WL = 16, DL = 17, GL = 15, IPF = 18, OPF = 21)
57 LAND_LINETYPES <- c(WL = "solid", DL = "longdash", GL = "dotdash", IPF = "dashed", OPF = "solid")
58 PADDY_SHAPES <- c("Non-paddy" = 21, "Paddy" = 24)
59 PADDY_LINETYPES <- c("Non-paddy" = "solid", "Paddy" = "longdash")
60
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61 ION_SPECS <- tibble::tribble(
62   ~ion_key, ~ion_label,
63   "K", "K+",
64   "Ca", "Ca2+",
65   "Na", "Na+",
66   "Mg", "Mg2+",
67   "CO3", "CO3^2-",
68   "HCO3", "HCO3-",
69   "SO4", "SO4^2-",
70   "Cl", "Cl-"
71 )
72 ION_LABELS <- c(K = "K+", Ca = "Ca2+", Na = "Na+", Mg = "Mg2+", CO3 = "CO 2-", HCO3 = "HCO -", SO4 = "SO 2-", Cl = "Cl-")
73 DEPTH_SPECS <- tibble::tribble(
74   ~depth_key, ~depth_label, ~depth_mid_cm, ~thickness_cm,
75   "0_20", "0-20", 10, 20,
76   "20_40", "20-40", 30, 20,
77   "40_60", "40-60", 50, 20
78 )
79
80 aggregate_specs <- c(
81   agg_gt2000 = "> 2000",
82   agg_1000_2000 = "1000-2000",
83   agg_500_1000 = "500-1000",
84   agg_250_500 = "250-500",
85   agg_53_250 = "53-250",
86   agg_lt53 = "< 53"
87 )
88 aggregate_labels <- c(
89   agg_gt2000 = ">2000 µm",
90   agg_1000_2000 = "1000-2000 µm",
91   agg_500_1000 = "500-1000 µm",
92   agg_250_500 = "250-500 µm",
93   agg_53_250 = "53-250 µm",
94   agg_lt53 = "<53 µm"
95 )
96 texture_specs <- c(
97   fine_clay = "Fine clay",
98   coarse_clay = "Coarse clay",
99   fine_silt = "Fine silt",
100  medium_silt = "Medium silt",
101  coarse_silt = "Coarse silt",
102  fine_sand = "Fine sand",
103  coarse_sand = "Coarse sand"
104 )
105 texture_labels <- c(
106  fine_clay = "Fine clay", coarse_clay = "Coarse clay",
107  fine_silt = "Fine silt", medium_silt = "Medium silt",
108  coarse_silt = "Coarse silt", fine_sand = "Fine sand",
109  coarse_sand = "Coarse sand"
110 )
111
112 safe_numeric <- function(x) suppressWarnings(as.numeric(x))
113
114 canonical_text <- function(x) {
115   x <- enc2utf8(as.character(x))
116   x <- gsub("\\r|\\n", " ", x)
117   replacements <- c(
118     "+" = "+", "-" = "-", "2" = "2", "3" = "3", "4" = "4",
119     " " = "0", "1" = "1", "2" = "2", "3" = "3", "4" = "4",
120     "-" = "-", "µ" = "µ", "µ" = "µ"

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121 )
122 for (needle in names(replacements)) x <- gsub(needle, replacements[[needle]], x, fixed = TRUE)
123 x <- gsub("\\s+", "", x)
124 tolower(x)
125 }
126
127 find_column <- function(data, include, starts_with = NULL, required = TRUE) {
128   nms <- names(data)
129   nms_norm <- canonical_text(nms)
130   keep <- rep(TRUE, length(nms))
131   for (term in include) keep <- keep & grepl(canonical_text(term), nms_norm, fixed = TRUE)
132   if (!is.null(starts_with)) keep <- keep & startsWith(nms_norm, canonical_text(starts_with))
133   hits <- nms[keep]
134   if (!length(hits)) {
135     if (required) stop("Missing column matching: ", paste(include, collapse = " + "))
136     return(NA_character_)
137   }
138   hits[1]
139 }
140
141 z_score <- function(x) {
142   x <- safe_numeric(x)
143   s <- stats::sd(x, na.rm = TRUE)
144   if (!is.finite(s) || s == 0) return(rep(0, length(x)))
145   as.numeric((x - mean(x, na.rm = TRUE)) / s)
146 }
147
148 standard_error <- function(x) {
149   n <- sum(is.finite(x))
150   if (n < 2) return(NA_real_)
151   stats::sd(x, na.rm = TRUE) / sqrt(n)
152 }
153
154 integrate_flux_to_g_m2 <- function(month, flux) {
155   ok <- is.finite(month) & is.finite(flux)
156   month <- month[ok]
157   flux <- flux[ok]
158   if (length(month) < 2L) return(NA_real_)
159   ord <- order(month)
160   month <- month[ord]
161   flux <- flux[ord]
162   delta_hours <- diff(month) * 30 * 24
163   sum((flux[-length(flux)] + flux[-1L]) / 2 * delta_hours) / 1000
164 }
165
166 p_symbol <- function(p) {
167   if (!is.finite(p)) return("")
168   if (p < 0.001) return("***")
169   if (p < 0.01) return("**")
170   if (p < 0.05) return("*")
171   if (p < 0.10) return("+")
172   "ns"
173 }
174
175 format_p <- function(p) {
176   if (!is.finite(p)) return("P = NA")
177   if (p < 0.001) return("P < 0.001")
178   paste0("P = ", formatC(p, digits = 3, format = "f"))
179 }
180
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181 pair_cor <- function(x, y, method = "pearson") {
182   ok <- is.finite(x) & is.finite(y)
183   x <- x[ok]
184   y <- y[ok]
185   n <- length(x)
186   if (n < 3 || stats::sd(x) == 0 || stats::sd(y) == 0) {
187     return(list(r = NA_real_, p = NA_real_, n = n, statistic = NA_real_))
188   }
189   r <- suppressWarnings(stats::cor(x, y, method = method, use = "complete.obs"))
190   if (!is.finite(r) || abs(r) >= 1) {
191     p <- if (is.finite(r) && abs(r) >= 1) 0 else NA_real_
192     return(list(r = r, p = p, n = n, statistic = NA_real_))
193   }
194   statistic <- r * sqrt((n - 2) / (1 - r^2))
195   p <- 2 * stats::pt(abs(statistic), df = n - 2, lower.tail = FALSE)
196   list(r = unname(r), p = unname(p), n = n, statistic = unname(statistic))
197 }
198
199 theme_sci <- function(base_size = 8, legend_position = "bottom") {
200   ggplot2::theme_minimal(base_family = "Arial", base_size = base_size) +
201     ggplot2::theme(
202       text = ggplot2::element_text(family = "Arial", colour = "#333333"),
203       plot.title = ggplot2::element_text(size = base_size + 1.4, face = "bold", hjust = 0),
204       plot.subtitle = ggplot2::element_text(size = base_size - 0.8, colour = "#555555", lineheight = 1),
205       axis.title = ggplot2::element_text(size = base_size + 0.3),
206       axis.text = ggplot2::element_text(size = base_size - 0.5, colour = "#333333"),
207       legend.text = ggplot2::element_text(size = base_size - 0.5),
208       legend.title = ggplot2::element_text(size = base_size, face = "bold"),
209       panel.background = ggplot2::element_rect(fill = "#FFFFFF", colour = NA),
210       plot.background = ggplot2::element_rect(fill = "#FFFFFF", colour = NA),
211       panel.grid.major = ggplot2::element_line(colour = "#E9E9E9", linewidth = 0.35),
212       panel.grid.minor = ggplot2::element_blank(),
213       axis.line = ggplot2::element_line(colour = "#333333", linewidth = 0.5),
214       axis.ticks = ggplot2::element_line(colour = "#333333", linewidth = 0.45),
215       strip.background = ggplot2::element_rect(fill = "#F7F7F7", colour = NA),
216       strip.text = ggplot2::element_text(size = base_size, face = "bold"),
217       legend.position = legend_position,
218       plot.margin = ggplot2::margin(5, 6, 5, 5)
219     )
220 }
221
222 land_scales <- function(use = c("colour", "fill", "shape", "linetype")) {
223   out <- list()
224   if ("colour" %in% use) out <- c(out, list(ggplot2::scale_colour_manual(values = LAND_COLORS, drop = FALSE)))
225   if ("fill" %in% use) out <- c(out, list(ggplot2::scale_fill_manual(values = LAND_COLORS, drop = FALSE)))
226   if ("shape" %in% use) out <- c(out, list(ggplot2::scale_shape_manual(values = LAND_SHAPES, drop = FALSE)))
227   if ("linetype" %in% use) out <- c(out, list(ggplot2::scale_linetype_manual(values = LAND_LINETYPES, drop = FALSE)))
228   out
229 }
230
231 save_plot <- function(plot, stem, width_mm, height_mm, dpi = 600) {
232   svg_path <- file.path(output_figures, paste0(stem, ".svg"))
233   png_path <- file.path(output_figures, paste0(stem, ".png"))
234   ggplot2::ggsave(svg_path, plot = plot, device = svglite::svglite, width = width_mm, height = height_mm, units = "mm", bg = "white")
235   ggplot2::ggsave(png_path, plot = plot, device = ragg::agg_png, width = width_mm, height = height_mm, units = "mm", dpi = dpi, bg = "white")
236   if (file.info(svg_path)$size < 1000 || file.info(png_path)$size < 1000) {
237     stop("Exported figure appears empty: ", stem)
238   }
239   c(svg = svg_path, png = png_path)
240 }

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241 read_project_data <- function() {
242   sheet <- readxl::excel_sheets(raw_xlsx)[1]
243   raw <- readxl::read_excel(raw_xlsx, sheet = sheet)
244   land <- toupper(trimws(as.character(raw[[find_column(raw, "Landtype")]])))
245   land[land == "FL"] <- "GL"
246   site <- trimws(as.character(raw[[find_column(raw, "Site")]]))
247   replicate <- trimws(as.character(raw[[find_column(raw, "Replicate")]]))
248
249   data <- tibble::tibble(
250     LandType = factor(land, levels = LAND_LEVELS),
251     Site = site,
252     Replicate = replicate,
253     Site_ID = factor(paste(land, site, sep = "-"), levels = SITE_LEVELS),
254     Sample_ID = paste(land, site, replicate, sep = "-"),
255     PaddyStatus = factor(ifelse(land %in% c("IPF", "OPF"), "Paddy", "Non-paddy"), levels = c("Non-paddy", "Paddy")),
256     pH = safe_numeric(raw[[find_column(raw, "pH")]]),
257     EC = safe_numeric(raw[[find_column(raw, "EC")]]),
258     MWD = safe_numeric(raw[[find_column(raw, "MWD")]])
259   )
260
261   for (depth_key in DEPTH_SPECS$depth_key) {
262     depth_label <- DEPTH_SPECS$depth_label[DEPTH_SPECS$depth_key == depth_key]
263     for (ion_key in ION_SPECS$ion_key) {
264       ion_label <- ION_LABELS[[ion_key]]
265       data[[paste("ion", ion_key, depth_key, sep = "_")]] <- safe_numeric(raw[[find_column(raw, c(depth_label, ion_label))]])
266     }
267   }
268
269   for (nm in names(aggregate_specs)) {
270     data[[nm]] <- safe_numeric(raw[[find_column(raw, c(aggregate_specs[[nm]], "µm"))]])
271   }
272
273   for (nm in names(texture_specs)) {
274     data[[nm]] <- safe_numeric(raw[[find_column(raw, texture_specs[[nm])]])
275   }
276
277   for (month in 5:10) {
278     data[[paste0("Temperature_", month)]] <- safe_numeric(raw[[find_column(raw, "Temperature", starts_with = paste0(month, " "))]])
279     data[[paste0("CO2_", month)]] <- safe_numeric(raw[[find_column(raw, "CO ", starts_with = paste0(month, " "))]])
280     data[[paste0("CH4_", month)]] <- safe_numeric(raw[[find_column(raw, "CH ", starts_with = paste0(month, " "))]])
281   }
282
283   data <- data |>
284   dplyr::filter(!is.na(LandType), !is.na(Site_ID), nzchar(as.character(Site)), nzchar(as.character(Replicate))) |>
285   dplyr::rowwise() |>
286   dplyr::mutate(
287     Na_burden_0_60 = sum(dplyr::c_across(dplyr::all_of(paste0("ion_Na_", DEPTH_SPECS$depth_key))) * DEPTH_SPECS$thickness_cm, na.rm = FALSE),
288     CO3_burden_0_60 = sum(dplyr::c_across(dplyr::all_of(paste0("ion_CO3_", DEPTH_SPECS$depth_key))) * DEPTH_SPECS$thickness_cm, na.rm = FALSE),
289     HCO3_burden_0_60 = sum(dplyr::c_across(dplyr::all_of(paste0("ion_HCO3_", DEPTH_SPECS$depth_key))) * DEPTH_SPECS$thickness_cm, na.rm = FALSE),
290     harmful_ion_burden_0_60 = Na_burden_0_60 + CO3_burden_0_60 + HCO3_burden_0_60,
291     CO2_cumulative_g_m2_season = integrate_flux_to_g_m2(5:10, dplyr::c_across(dplyr::all_of(paste0("CO2_", 5:10)))),
292     CH4_cumulative_g_m2_season = integrate_flux_to_g_m2(5:10, dplyr::c_across(dplyr::all_of(paste0("CH4_", 5:10)))),
293     CH4_CO2eq_g_m2_season = CH4_cumulative_g_m2_season * 27,
294     direct_ghg_cost_g_m2_season = CO2_cumulative_g_m2_season + CH4_CO2eq_g_m2_season,
295     Temperature_mean = mean(dplyr::c_across(dplyr::all_of(paste0("Temperature_", 5:10))), na.rm = TRUE),
296     CO2_mean = mean(dplyr::c_across(dplyr::all_of(paste0("CO2_", 5:10))), na.rm = TRUE),
297     CH4_mean = mean(dplyr::c_across(dplyr::all_of(paste0("CH4_", 5:10))), na.rm = TRUE)
298   ) |>
299   dplyr::ungroup()
300

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```
301 data
302 }
303
304 site_means_from_samples <- function(samples) {
305   numeric_cols <- names(samples)[vapply(samples, is.numeric, logical(1))]
306   out <- samples |>
307     dplyr::group_by(LandType, Site_ID, PaddyStatus) |>
308     dplyr::summarise(
309       n_replicates = dplyr::n(),
310       dplyr::across(dplyr::all_of(numeric_cols), ~mean(.x, na.rm = TRUE)),
311       .groups = "drop"
312     ) |>
313     dplyr::mutate(
314       LandType = factor(as.character(LandType), levels = LAND_LEVELS),
315       Site_ID = factor(as.character(Site_ID), levels = SITE_LEVELS),
316       PaddyStatus = factor(as.character(PaddyStatus), levels = c("Non-paddy", "Paddy"))
317     )
318   out |>
319     dplyr::mutate(
320       MWD_z = z_score(MWD),
321       harmful_ion_burden_z = z_score(harmful_ion_burden_0_60),
322       restoration_benefit = MWD_z - harmful_ion_burden_z
323     )
324 }
325
326 mean_se_summary <- function(data, group_vars, value_vars) {
327   data |>
328     dplyr::group_by(dplyr::across(dplyr::all_of(group_vars))) |>
329     dplyr::summarise(
330       dplyr::across(
331         dplyr::all_of(value_vars),
332         list(n = ~sum(is.finite(.x)), mean = ~mean(.x, na.rm = TRUE), SE = ~standard_error(.x)),
333         .names = "{.col}_{.fn}"
334       ),
335       .groups = "drop"
336     )
337 }
338
339 model_term_rows <- function(fit, analysis, response_label) {
340   frame <- stats::model.frame(fit)
341   formula_text <- paste(deparse(stats::formula(fit)), collapse = " ")
342   sm <- summary(fit)
343   r2 <- if (!is.null(sm$r.squared)) unname(sm$r.squared) else NA_real_
344   adj_r2 <- if (!is.null(sm$adj.r.squared)) unname(sm$adj.r.squared) else NA_real_
345   coef_tbl <- as.data.frame(sm$coefficients)
346   coef_tbl$term <- rownames(coef_tbl)
347   rownames(coef_tbl) <- NULL
348   ci <- tryCatch(stats::confint(fit), error = function(e) NULL)
349   if (is.null(ci)) {
350     coef_tbl$CI_low <- NA_real_
351     coef_tbl$CI_high <- NA_real_
352   } else {
353     coef_tbl$CI_low <- ci[coef_tbl$term, 1]
354     coef_tbl$CI_high <- ci[coef_tbl$term, 2]
355   }
356   coef_rows <- tibble::tibble(
357     analysis = analysis,
358     response = response_label,
359     formula = formula_text,
360     n = nrow(frame),
```

```

361 R2 = r2,
362 adjusted_R2 = adj_r2,
363 row_type = "coefficient",
364 term = coef_tbl$term,
365 estimate = coef_tbl[["Estimate"]],
366 SE = coef_tbl[["Std. Error"]],
367 CI_low = coef_tbl$CI_low,
368 CI_high = coef_tbl$CI_high,
369 statistic = coef_tbl[["t value"]],
370 df1 = NA_real_,
371 df2 = stats::df.residual(fit),
372 p_value = coef_tbl[["Pr(>|t|)"]],
373 significance = vapply(coef_tbl[["Pr(>|t|)"]], p_symbol, character(1))
374 )
375
376 an <- as.data.frame(stats::anova(fit))
377 an$term <- rownames(an)
378 rownames(an) <- NULL
379 an <- an[an$term != "Residuals", , drop = FALSE]
380 an_rows <- tibble::tibble()
381 if (nrow(an)) {
382   an_rows <- tibble::tibble(
383     analysis = analysis,
384     response = response_label,
385     formula = formula_text,
386     n = nrow(frame),
387     R2 = r2,
388     adjusted_R2 = adj_r2,
389     row_type = "model_term",
390     term = an$term,
391     estimate = NA_real_,
392     SE = NA_real_,
393     CI_low = NA_real_,
394     CI_high = NA_real_,
395     statistic = an[["F value"]],
396     df1 = an[["Df"]],
397     df2 = stats::df.residual(fit),
398     p_value = an[["Pr(>F)"]],
399     significance = vapply(an[["Pr(>F)"]], p_symbol, character(1))
400   )
401 }
402 dplyr::bind_rows(coef_rows, an_rows)
403 }
404
405 letter_summary <- function(data, value_col, group_col, group_levels) {
406   d <- data |>
407     dplyr::filter(is.finite(.data[[value_col]]), !is.na(.data[[group_col]])) |>
408     dplyr::mutate(Group = factor(as.character(.data[[group_col]]), levels = group_levels), Value = .data[[value_col]])
409   fit <- stats::lm(Value ~ Group, data = d)
410   letters_df <- tryCatch({
411     emm <- emmeans::emmeans(fit, specs = ~ Group)
412     cld <- suppressMessages(suppressWarnings(multcomp::cld(emm, adjust = "none", Letters = letters, sort = FALSE)))
413     tibble::tibble(Group = as.character(cld$Group), Letter = gsub("\\s+", "", cld$.group))
414   }, error = function(e) tibble::tibble(Group = group_levels, Letter = ""))
415   d |>
416     dplyr::group_by(Group) |>
417     dplyr::summarise(n = dplyr::n(), mean = mean(Value, na.rm = TRUE), SE = standard_error(Value), .groups = "drop") |>
418     dplyr::left_join(letters_df, by = "Group") |>
419     dplyr::mutate(Group = factor(Group, levels = group_levels))
420 }

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```

421
422 write_core_tables <- function(samples, sites) {
423   readr::write_csv(samples, file.path(output_tables, "public_sample_level_derived_data.csv"))
424   readr::write_csv(sites, file.path(output_tables, "public_site_level_derived_data.csv"))
425   readr::write_csv(
426     mean_se_summary(
427       sites,
428       "LandType",
429       c("pH", "EC", "MWD", "harmful_ion_burden_0_60", "CO2_cumulative_g_m2_season", "CH4_cumulative_g_m2_season", "CH4_CO2eq_g_m2_season", "direct_ghg_cost_g_m2_season")
430     ),
431     file.path(output_tables, "public_landtype_site_mean_summary.csv")
432   )
433 }
434
435 build_ion_long <- function(samples, aggregate_to_site = TRUE) {
436   long <- dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(seq_len(nrow(DEPTH_SPECS)), function(i) {
437     depth_key <- DEPTH_SPECS$depth_key[i]
438     depth_label <- DEPTH_SPECS$depth_label[i]
439     depth_mid <- DEPTH_SPECS$depth_mid_cm[i]
440     dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(ION_SPECS$ion_key, function(ion_key) {
441       tibble::tibble(
442         LandType = samples$LandType,
443         Site_ID = samples$Site_ID,
444         Replicate = samples$Replicate,
445         Ion = factor(ION_LABELS[[ion_key]], levels = unname(ION_LABELS)),
446         IonKey = factor(ion_key, levels = ION_SPECS$ion_key),
447         Depth = factor(depth_label, levels = DEPTH_SPECS$depth_label),
448         DepthMid = depth_mid,
449         Value = samples[[paste("ion", ion_key, depth_key, sep = "_")]]
450       )
451     })))
452   })
453   if (!aggregate_to_site) return(long)
454   long |>
455     dplyr::group_by(LandType, Site_ID, Ion, IonKey, Depth, DepthMid) |>
456     dplyr::summarise(Value = mean(Value, na.rm = TRUE), .groups = "drop")
457 }
458
459 run_statistical_analyses <- function(samples, sites) {
460   soil_rows <- dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(c("pH", "EC"), function(v) {
461     fit <- stats::lm(stats::as.formula(paste(v, "~ LandType")), data = sites)
462     model_term_rows(fit, "LandType effect on site-level soil chemistry", v)
463   })))
464
465   ion_long_site <- build_ion_long(samples, aggregate_to_site = TRUE)
466   ion_rows <- dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(levels(ion_long_site$IonKey), function(ion_key) {
467     d <- ion_long_site |>
468       dplyr::filter(IonKey == ion_key, is.finite(Value)) |>
469       dplyr::mutate(Depth = factor(as.character(Depth), levels = DEPTH_SPECS$depth_label))
470     fit <- stats::lm(Value ~ LandType * Depth, data = d)
471     model_term_rows(fit, "LandType x Depth ion profile model on site means", ION_LABELS[[ion_key]])
472   })))
473
474   harmful_fit <- stats::lm(harmful_ion_burden_0_60 ~ LandType, data = sites)
475   harmful_rows <- model_term_rows(harmful_fit, "LandType effect on 0-60 cm harmful ion burden", "harmful_ion_burden_0_60")
476
477   agg_vars <- c("MWD", names(aggregate_specs))
478   aggregate_rows <- dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(agg_vars, function(v) {
479     fit <- stats::lm(stats::as.formula(paste(v, "~ LandType")), data = sites)

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```
480   model_term_rows(fit, "LandType effect on aggregate variables", v)
481   })
482
483   ghg_vars <- c("CO2_cumulative_g_m2_season", "CH4_cumulative_g_m2_season", "CH4_CO2eq_g_m2_season", "direct_ghg_cost_g_m2_season")
484   ghg_rows <- dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(ghg_vars, function(v) {
485     dplyr::bind_rows(
486       model_term_rows(stats::lm(stats::as.formula(paste(v, "~ LandType")), data = sites), "LandType effect on seasonal gas metrics", v),
487       model_term_rows(stats::lm(stats::as.formula(paste(v, "~ PaddyStatus")), data = sites), "PaddyStatus effect on seasonal gas metrics", v)
488     )
489   })
490
491   trade_specs <- list(
492     c("CH4_cumulative_g_m2_season", "restoration_benefit"),
493     c("CO2_cumulative_g_m2_season", "restoration_benefit"),
494     c("CH4_CO2eq_g_m2_season", "restoration_benefit"),
495     c("direct_ghg_cost_g_m2_season", "restoration_benefit"),
496     c("CH4_CO2eq_g_m2_season", "MWD"),
497     c("CH4_CO2eq_g_m2_season", "harmful_ion_burden_0_60"),
498     c("direct_ghg_cost_g_m2_season", "MWD"),
499     c("direct_ghg_cost_g_m2_season", "harmful_ion_burden_0_60")
500   )
501   trade_rows <- dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(trade_specs, function(spec) {
502     formula_text <- paste(spec[1], "~", spec[2], "* PaddyStatus")
503     fit <- stats::lm(stats::as.formula(formula_text), data = sites)
504     model_term_rows(fit, "Site-level restoration-climate trade-off ANCOVA", paste(spec[1], "vs", spec[2]))
505   })
506
507   temp_flux <- build_temperature_flux_data(samples)
508   temp_rows <- dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(levels(temp_flux$Gas), function(gas) {
509     d <- temp_flux |>
510       dplyr::filter(Gas == gas)
511     fit <- stats::lm(Flux_z ~ Temperature * PaddyStatus, data = d)
512     model_term_rows(fit, "Monthly temperature-flux relationship", gas)
513   })
514
515   relation_pairs <- dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(
516     list(
517       c("MWD", "harmful_ion_burden_0_60"),
518       c("restoration_benefit", "CH4_CO2eq_g_m2_season"),
519       c("restoration_benefit", "direct_ghg_cost_g_m2_season"),
520       c("MWD", "CH4_CO2eq_g_m2_season"),
521       c("harmful_ion_burden_0_60", "CH4_CO2eq_g_m2_season")
522     ),
523     function(pair) {
524       pc <- pair_cor(sites[[pair[1]]], sites[[pair[2]]], "pearson")
525       tibble::tibble(
526         x_variable = pair[1],
527         y_variable = pair[2],
528         method = "pearson",
529         n = pc$n,
530         estimate = pc$r,
531         statistic = pc$statistic,
532         p_value = pc$p,
533         significance = p_symbol(pc$p)
534       )
535     }
536   ))
537
538   readr::write_csv(soil_rows, file.path(output_tables, "public_soil_chemistry_model_terms.csv"))
539   readr::write_csv(ion_rows, file.path(output_tables, "public_ion_profile_model_terms.csv"))
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540 readr::write_csv(harmful_rows, file.path(output_tables, "public_harmful_ion_burden_model_terms.csv"))
541 readr::write_csv(aggregate_rows, file.path(output_tables, "public_aggregate_model_terms.csv"))
542 readr::write_csv(ghg_rows, file.path(output_tables, "public_greenhouse_gas_model_terms.csv"))
543 readr::write_csv(trade_rows, file.path(output_tables, "public_tradeoff_model_terms.csv"))
544 readr::write_csv(temp_rows, file.path(output_tables, "public_temperature_flux_model_terms.csv"))
545 readr::write_csv(relation_pairs, file.path(output_tables, "public_key_correlation_regression_pairs.csv"))
546
547 invisible(list(
548   soil = soil_rows, ion = ion_rows, harmful = harmful_rows, aggregate = aggregate_rows,
549   gas = ghg_rows, trade = trade_rows, temperature = temp_rows, pairs = relation_pairs
550 ))
551 }
552
553 build_temperature_flux_data <- function(samples) {
554   dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(5:10, function(month) {
555     dplyr::bind_rows(
556       tibble::tibble(
557         Temperature = samples[[paste0("Temperature_", month)]],
558         LandType = samples$LandType,
559         PaddyStatus = samples$PaddyStatus,
560         Gas = "CO2",
561         Flux = samples[[paste0("CO2_", month)]]
562       ),
563       tibble::tibble(
564         Temperature = samples[[paste0("Temperature_", month)]],
565         LandType = samples$LandType,
566         PaddyStatus = samples$PaddyStatus,
567         Gas = "CH4",
568         Flux = samples[[paste0("CH4_", month)]]
569       )
570     )
571   }))) |>
572   dplyr::mutate(
573     Gas = factor(Gas, levels = c("CO2", "CH4")),
574     TrendGroup = factor(paste(as.character(Gas), as.character(PaddyStatus)), levels = c("CO2 Non-paddy", "CO2 Paddy", "CH4 Non-paddy", "CH4 Paddy"))
575   ) |>
576   dplyr::group_by(Gas) |>
577   dplyr::mutate(Flux_z = z_score(Flux)) |>
578   dplyr::ungroup() |>
579   dplyr::filter(is.finite(Temperature), is.finite(Flux_z), !is.na(PaddyStatus), !is.na(TrendGroup))
580 }
581
582 make_fig2_ph_ec <- function(samples) {
583   pe <- tidyr::pivot_longer(samples, cols = dplyr::all_of(c("pH", "EC")), names_to = "Variable", values_to = "Value")
584   pe$Variable <- factor(pe$Variable, levels = c("pH", "EC"), labels = c("pH", "EC (mS cm-1)"))
585   pc <- pair_cor(samples$pH, samples$EC, "pearson")
586   p_text <- paste0("r = ", formatC(pc$r, digits = 2, format = "f"), "\n", if (pc$p < 0.001) "P < 0.001" else format_p(pc$p))
587
588   p_a <- ggplot2::ggplot(pe, ggplot2::aes(LandType, Value, fill = LandType, colour = LandType)) +
589     ggdist::stat_halfeye(adjust = 0.65, width = 0.65, justification = -0.18, alpha = 0.35, point_colour = NA) +
590     ggplot2::geom_boxplot(width = 0.18, fill = "white", colour = "#222222", linewidth = 0.35, outlier.shape = NA) +
591     ggplot2::geom_jitter(ggplot2::aes(shape = LandType), width = 0.10, size = 1.7, alpha = 0.55, stroke = 0.25) +
592     ggplot2::facet_wrap(~Variable, scales = "free_y", nrow = 1) +
593     land_scales(c("colour", "fill", "shape")) +
594     ggplot2::labs(title = "Observed pH and EC distributions", x = NULL, y = NULL) +
595     theme_sci() +
596     ggplot2::theme(legend.position = "none")
597
598   p_b <- ggplot2::ggplot(samples, ggplot2::aes(pH, EC)) +
599     ggplot2::geom_smooth(method = "lm", se = TRUE, colour = "#777777", fill = "#D9D9D9", linewidth = 0.7, alpha = 0.35) +

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600 ggplot2::geom_point(ggplot2::aes(shape = LandType), colour = "white", size = 3.0, alpha = 0.75) +
601 ggplot2::geom_point(ggplot2::aes(colour = LandType, shape = LandType, size = ion_Na_0_20), alpha = 0.65, stroke = 0.3) +
602   land_scales(c("colour", "shape")) +
603 ggplot2::scale_size_continuous(name = "Na+ (0-20 cm)\n(cmolc kg-1)", range = c(1.6, 5.2)) +
604 ggplot2::annotate("label", x = -Inf, y = Inf, label = p_text, hjust = -0.08, vjust = 1.15, family = "Arial", size = 7.5 / ggplot2::.pt, linewidth = 0.2, fill = "white") +
605 ggplot2::labs(title = "Coupled pH-EC gradient", x = "pH", y = "EC (mS cm-1)") +
606   theme_sci()
607
608 final <- (p_a | p_b) +
609   patchwork::plot_layout(guides = "keep") +
610   patchwork::plot_annotation(tag_levels = "A") &
611   ggplot2::theme(plot.tag = ggplot2::element_text(family = "Arial", face = "bold", size = 12, colour = "#111111"))
612   save_plot(final, "public_Fig2_pH_EC", 180, 85)
613 }
614
615 format_ion_value <- function(x) {
616   out <- rep("", length(x))
617   ok <- is.finite(x)
618   out[ok & abs(x) < 1] <- trimws(formatC(x[ok & abs(x) < 1], digits = 2, format = "f"))
619   out[ok & abs(x) >= 1] <- trimws(formatC(x[ok & abs(x) >= 1], digits = 2, format = "fg"))
620   out
621 }
622
623 interpolate_depth_profile <- function(depth, value, depth_out) {
624   ok <- is.finite(depth) & is.finite(value)
625   if (sum(ok) == 0) return(rep(NA_real_, length(depth_out)))
626   if (sum(ok) == 1) return(rep(value[ok][1], length(depth_out)))
627   x <- depth[ok]
628   y <- value[ok]
629   ord <- order(x)
630   x <- x[ord]
631   y <- y[ord]
632   keep <- !duplicated(x)
633   x <- x[keep]
634   y <- y[keep]
635   if (length(x) == 1) return(rep(y[1], length(depth_out)))
636   smoothed <- rep(NA_real_, length(depth_out))
637   for (i in seq_len(length(x) - 1)) {
638     idx <- depth_out >= x[i] & depth_out <= x[i + 1]
639     if (!any(idx)) next
640     u <- (depth_out[idx] - x[i]) / (x[i + 1] - x[i])
641     u <- pmin(pmax(u, 0), 1)
642     s <- u * u * u * (u * (u * 6 - 15) + 10)
643     smoothed[idx] <- y[i] + (y[i + 1] - y[i]) * s
644   }
645   smoothed[is.na(smoothed)] <- stats::approx(x, y, xout = depth_out[is.na(smoothed)], rule = 2, ties = "ordered")$y
646   value_range <- range(y, na.rm = TRUE)
647   pmin(pmax(smoothed, value_range[1]), value_range[2])
648 }
649
650 make_fig3_ions <- function(samples) {
651   profile <- build_ion_long(samples, aggregate_to_site = FALSE)
652   profile_sum <- profile |>
653     dplyr::group_by(LandType, Ion, IonKey, Depth, DepthMid) |>
654     dplyr::summarise(n = sum(is.finite(Value)), Mean = mean(Value, na.rm = TRUE), SE = standard_error(Value), .groups = "drop") |>
655     dplyr::mutate(LandIndex = as.numeric(factor(LandType, levels = LAND_LEVELS)), Label = format_ion_value(Mean))
656
657   depth_grid <- seq(0.05, 59.95, by = 0.1)
658   smooth_profile <- dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(split(profile_sum, list(profile_sum$Ion, profile_sum$LandType), drop = TRUE), function(x) {

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659   x <- x[order(x$DepthMid), ]
660   anchor_depth <- c(0, x$DepthMid, 60)
661   anchor_value <- c(x$Mean[which.min(abs(x$DepthMid - 10))], x$Mean, x$Mean[which.min(abs(x$DepthMid - 50))])
662   tibble::tibble(
663     LandType = x$LandType[1],
664     Ion = x$Ion[1],
665     IonKey = x$IonKey[1],
666     LandIndex = x$LandIndex[1],
667     Depth = depth_grid,
668     Value = interpolate_depth_profile(anchor_depth, anchor_value, depth_grid)
669   )
670 })
671
672 make_panel <- function(ion_label, panel_index) {
673   panel_smooth <- smooth_profile[smooth_profile$Ion == ion_label, , drop = FALSE]
674   panel_points <- profile_sum[profile_sum$Ion == ion_label, , drop = FALSE]
675   show_y <- panel_index %in% c(1, 5)
676   show_x_title <- panel_index > 4
677   ggplot2::ggplot(panel_smooth, ggplot2::aes(LandIndex, Depth, fill = Value)) +
678     ggplot2::geom_tile(width = 1, height = 0.1) +
679     ggplot2::geom_hline(yintercept = c(20, 40), colour = "#FFFFFF", linewidth = 0.12, alpha = 0.26) +
680     ggplot2::geom_point(data = panel_points, ggplot2::aes(LandIndex, DepthMid), inherit.aes = FALSE, shape = 21, size = 1.15, stroke = 0.24, colour = "#8A8A8A", fill = "#FFFFFF") +
681     ggplot2::geom_text(data = panel_points, ggplot2::aes(LandIndex, DepthMid + 4.2, label = Label), inherit.aes = FALSE, family = "Arial", size = 5.8 / ggplot2::.pt, colour = "#4E4E4E") +
682     ggplot2::scale_x_continuous(limits = c(0.5, length(LAND_LEVELS) + 0.5), breaks = seq_along(LAND_LEVELS), labels = LAND_LEVELS, expand = c(0, 0)) +
683     ggplot2::scale_y_reverse(limits = c(60, 0), breaks = c(0, 20, 40, 60), expand = c(0, 0)) +
684     ggplot2::scale_fill_gradientn(colours = c("#F7FBFF", "#DBEAF4", "#9ECAE1", "#163D73"), name = "cmolc kg-1", na.value = "#F7FBFF") +
685     ggplot2::labs(title = as.character(ion_label), x = if (show_x_title) "LandType" else NULL, y = if (show_y) "Soil depth (cm)" else NULL) +
686     theme_sci(base_size = 7.2, legend_position = "right") +
687     ggplot2::theme(
688       plot.title = ggplot2::element_text(size = 8.4, face = "bold", hjust = 0.5, colour = "#111111"),
689       axis.line = ggplot2::element_blank(), panel.grid = ggplot2::element_blank(),
690       panel.border = ggplot2::element_rect(fill = NA, colour = "#333333", linewidth = 0.42),
691       legend.title = ggplot2::element_text(size = 5.8),
692       legend.text = ggplot2::element_text(size = 5.8),
693       plot.margin = ggplot2::margin(3, 4, 3, 3)
694     ) +
695     {if (!show_y) ggplot2::theme(axis.title.y = ggplot2::element_blank(), axis.text.y = ggplot2::element_blank(), axis.ticks.y = ggplot2::element_blank())}
696 }
697
698 ion_panels <- lapply(seq_along(ION_LABELS), function(i) make_panel(unnamed(ION_LABELS)[i], i))
699 p_a <- patchwork::wrap_elements(full = patchwork::wrap_plots(ion_panels, ncol = 4, guides = "keep"))
700
701 burden_mean <- profile_sum |>
702   dplyr::group_by(LandType, Ion, IonKey) |>
703   dplyr::summarise(Burden = sum(Mean * 20, na.rm = TRUE), .groups = "drop") |>
704   dplyr::group_by(Ion) |>
705   dplyr::mutate(Z = z_score(Burden)) |>
706   dplyr::ungroup() |>
707   dplyr::mutate(LandType = factor(LandType, levels = rev(LAND_LEVELS)), Ion = factor(Ion, levels = unnamed(ION_LABELS)))
708 readr::write_csv(burden_mean, file.path(output_tables, "public_ion_burden_landtype_means.csv"))
709 z_limit <- max(abs(burden_mean$Z), na.rm = TRUE)
710 if (!is.finite(z_limit) || z_limit == 0) z_limit <- -1
711
712 p_b <- ggplot2::ggplot(burden_mean, ggplot2::aes(Ion, LandType, fill = Z)) +
713   ggplot2::geom_tile(colour = "#FFFFFF", linewidth = 0.72) +
714   ggplot2::geom_text(ggplot2::aes(label = formatC(Z, digits = 2, format = "f")), family = "Arial", size = 6.8 / ggplot2::.pt, colour = "#2F2F2F") +
715   ggplot2::scale_fill_gradient2(low = "#D8E8F2", mid = "#F7F7F7", high = "#BD5E5E", midpoint = 0, limits = c(-z_limit, z_limit), name = "Within-ion\nz-score") +
716   ggplot2::labs(title = "Cumulative ion burdens across the 0-60 cm profile", subtitle = "Cumulative burden = Σ(layer mean × 20 cm)", x = NULL, y = NULL) +

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717   theme_sci(base_size = 8, legend_position = "right") +
718   ggplot2::theme(axis.line = ggplot2::element_blank(), axis.ticks = ggplot2::element_blank(), panel.grid = ggplot2::element_blank())
719
720   final <- p_a / p_b +
721     patchwork::plot_layout(heights = c(3.1, 1), guides = "keep") +
722     patchwork::plot_annotation(tag_levels = "A") &
723     ggplot2::theme(plot.tag = ggplot2::element_text(family = "Arial", face = "bold", size = 15, colour = "#111111"))
724   save_plot(final, "public_Fig3_ion_profiles", 190, 160)
725 }
726
727 make_fig4_aggregates <- function(samples) {
728   agg_vars <- names(aggregate_specs)
729   agg_colors <- c("#8C4900", "#A9621E", "#C87E33", "#DFA65B", "#EBD8B4", "#B8C4CC")
730   names(agg_colors) <- aggregate_labels[agg_vars]
731   agg <- samples |>
732     dplyr::group_by(LandType) |>
733     dplyr::summarise(dplyr::across(dplyr::all_of(agg_vars), ~mean(.x, na.rm = TRUE)), .groups = "drop") |>
734     tidyr::pivot_longer(~LandType, names_to = "Class", values_to = "Proportion") |>
735     dplyr::mutate(Class = factor(Class, levels = agg_vars, labels = aggregate_labels[agg_vars]))
736
737   p_a <- ggplot2::ggplot(agg, ggplot2::aes(x = LandType, stratum = Class, alluvium = Class, y = Proportion, fill = Class)) +
738     ggalluvial::geom_flow(alpha = 0.55, colour = "white", linewidth = 0.25) +
739     ggalluvial::geom_stratum(width = 0.30, colour = "white", linewidth = 0.3) +
740     ggplot2::scale_fill_manual(values = agg_colors) +
741     ggplot2::scale_y_continuous(limits = c(0, 105), breaks = c(0, 25, 50, 75, 100)) +
742     ggplot2::labs(title = "Aggregate-size composition flow", x = NULL, y = "Proportion (%)", fill = "Aggregate size") +
743     theme_sci(base_size = 8.4, legend_position = "bottom") +
744     ggplot2::guides(fill = ggplot2::guide_legend(nrow = 2, byrow = TRUE))
745
746   p_b <- ggplot2::ggplot(samples, ggplot2::aes(LandType, MWD, fill = LandType, colour = LandType)) +
747     ggdist::stat_halfeye(adjust = 0.7, width = 0.7, justification = -0.18, alpha = 0.35, point_colour = NA) +
748     ggplot2::geom_boxplot(width = 0.18, fill = "white", colour = "#222222", linewidth = 0.35, outlier.shape = NA) +
749     ggplot2::geom_jitter(ggplot2::aes(shape = LandType), width = 0.10, size = 1.8, alpha = 0.60, stroke = 0.25) +
750     land_scales(c("colour", "fill", "shape")) +
751     ggplot2::labs(title = "MWD recovery across land uses", x = NULL, y = "MWD (mm)") +
752     theme_sci(base_size = 8.4, legend_position = "bottom") +
753     ggplot2::guides(fill = ggplot2::guide_legend(nrow = 1), colour = "none", shape = "none")
754
755   texture_vars <- names(texture_specs)
756   texture_colors <- c("#5B4A3F", "#7E6654", "#9E846B", "#B9A087", "#D0B99E", "#E2CFB2", "#F0E2C9")
757   names(texture_colors) <- texture_labels[texture_vars]
758   texture_data <- samples |>
759     dplyr::mutate(
760       clay = fine_clay + coarse_clay,
761       silt = fine_silt + medium_silt + coarse_silt,
762       sand = fine_sand + coarse_sand,
763       tern_x = silt / 100 + 0.5 * clay / 100,
764       tern_y = sqrt(3) / 2 * clay / 100
765     )
766   triangle <- data.frame(x = c(0, 1, 0.5, 0), y = c(0, 0, sqrt(3) / 2, 0))
767   p_c <- ggplot2::ggplot(texture_data, ggplot2::aes(tern_x, tern_y)) +
768     ggplot2::geom_path(data = triangle, ggplot2::aes(x, y), inherit.aes = FALSE, colour = "#444444", linewidth = 0.6) +
769     ggplot2::geom_point(ggplot2::aes(shape = LandType), colour = "white", size = 3.3, alpha = 0.85) +
770     ggplot2::geom_point(ggplot2::aes(colour = LandType, shape = LandType), size = 2.4, alpha = 0.75, stroke = 0.35) +
771     land_scales(c("colour", "shape")) +
772     ggplot2::annotate("text", x = -0.03, y = -0.035, label = "Sand", family = "Arial", size = 7.5 / ggplot2::.pt, hjust = 0) +
773     ggplot2::annotate("text", x = 1.03, y = -0.035, label = "Silt", family = "Arial", size = 7.5 / ggplot2::.pt, hjust = 1) +
774     ggplot2::annotate("text", x = 0.5, y = sqrt(3) / 2 + 0.035, label = "Clay", family = "Arial", size = 7.5 / ggplot2::.pt) +
775     ggplot2::coord_equal(xlim = c(-0.08, 1.08), ylim = c(-0.07, 0.94), clip = "off") +
776     ggplot2::labs(title = "Texture ternary background") +

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777 theme_sci(base_size = 8.4, legend_position = "bottom") +
778 ggplot2::theme(axis.title = ggplot2::element_blank(), axis.text = ggplot2::element_blank(), axis.ticks = ggplot2::element_blank(), axis.line = ggplot2::element_blank())
779
780 texture_site <- samples |>
781 tidyr::pivot_longer(dplyr::all_of(texture_vars), names_to = "Class", values_to = "Proportion") |>
782 dplyr::group_by(Site_ID, Class) |>
783 dplyr::summarise(Proportion = mean(Proportion, na.rm = TRUE), .groups = "drop") |>
784 dplyr::mutate(Site_ID = factor(Site_ID, levels = SITE_LEVELS), Class = factor(Class, levels = texture_vars, labels = texture_labels[texture_vars]))
785 p_d <- ggplot2::ggplot(texture_site, ggplot2::aes(Site_ID, Proportion, fill = Class)) +
786 ggplot2::geom_col(width = 0.82, colour = "white", linewidth = 0.18) +
787 ggplot2::scale_fill_manual(values = texture_colors) +
788 ggplot2::scale_y_continuous(limits = c(0, 108), breaks = c(0, 25, 50, 75, 100)) +
789 ggplot2::labs(title = "Seven particle-size fractions", x = NULL, y = "Proportion (%)", fill = "Particle size") +
790 theme_sci(base_size = 8.4, legend_position = "right") +
791 ggplot2::theme(axis.text.x = ggplot2::element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1))
792
793 final <- ((p_a | p_b) / (p_c | p_d)) +
794 patchwork::plot_layout(widths = c(1, 1.08), heights = c(1, 1.15), guides = "keep") +
795 patchwork::plot_annotation(tag_levels = "A") &
796 ggplot2::theme(plot.tag = ggplot2::element_text(family = "Arial", face = "bold", size = 14, colour = "#111111"))
797 save_plot(final, "public_Fig4_aggregates", 203.2, 210.6)
798 }
799
800 fixed_letter_y <- function(value, pad = 0.10) {
801   rng <- range(value, na.rm = TRUE)
802   span <- diff(rng)
803   if (!is.finite(span) || span == 0) span <- max(abs(rng), na.rm = TRUE)
804   if (!is.finite(span) || span == 0) span <- 1
805   list(bottom = rng[1] - span * 0.06, letter = rng[2] + span * pad, top = rng[2] + span * (pad + 0.12))
806 }
807
808 make_fig5_greenhouse_gas <- function(samples) {
809   monthly <- dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(c("Temperature", "CO2", "CH4"), function(metric) {
810     cols <- paste0(metric, "_", 5:10)
811     out <- tidyr::pivot_longer(samples, cols = dplyr::all_of(cols), names_to = "Month", values_to = "Value")
812     out$Month <- as.integer(sub(paste0(metric, "_"), "", out$Month, fixed = TRUE))
813     out$Variable <- metric
814     out
815   })))
816   monthly_sum <- monthly |>
817     dplyr::group_by(LandType, Variable, Month) |>
818     dplyr::summarise(Mean = mean(Value, na.rm = TRUE), SE = standard_error(Value), .groups = "drop")
819
820   season_panel <- function(metric, ylab, title) {
821     x <- monthly_sum[monthly_sum$Variable == metric, ]
822     ggplot2::ggplot(x, ggplot2::aes(Month, Mean, colour = LandType, fill = LandType, shape = LandType, linetype = LandType, group = LandType)) +
823       ggplot2::geom_ribbon(ggplot2::aes(ymin = Mean - SE, ymax = Mean + SE), colour = NA, alpha = 0.15) +
824       ggplot2::geom_line(linewidth = 0.8) +
825       ggplot2::geom_point(size = 2.3, stroke = 0.35) +
826       land_scales() +
827       ggplot2::scale_x_continuous(breaks = 5:10) +
828       ggplot2::labs(title = title, x = "Month", y = ylab) +
829       theme_sci(base_size = 8.1, legend_position = "bottom") +
830       ggplot2::guides(fill = "none", shape = "none", linetype = "none")
831   }
832
833   p_a <- season_panel("Temperature", "Temperature (°C)", "Temperature dynamics")
834   p_b <- season_panel("CO2", "CO flux (mg m-2 h-1)", "CO midsummer plateau")
835   p_c <- season_panel("CH4", "CH flux (mg m-2 h-1)", "CH earlier peak and decline")

```

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836
837 cumulative_panel <- function(variable, title, y_label, annotate_paddy = FALSE) {
838   stats <- letter_summary(samples, variable, "LandType", LAND_LEVELS)
839   sample <- samples |>
840     dplyr::select(LandType, dplyr::all_of(variable)) |>
841     dplyr::rename(Value = dplyr::all_of(variable))
842   y_pos <- fixed_letter_y(sample$Value)
843   stats <- stats |>
844     dplyr::mutate(LandType = factor(as.character(Group), levels = LAND_LEVELS), label_y = y_pos$letter)
845   p <- ggplot2::ggplot(sample, ggplot2::aes(x = LandType, y = Value, fill = LandType, colour = LandType)) +
846     ggdist::stat_halfeye(adjust = 0.65, width = 0.65, justification = -0.18, alpha = 0.35, point_colour = NA, .width = 0, show.legend = FALSE) +
847     ggplot2::geom_boxplot(width = 0.18, fill = "white", colour = "#222222", linewidth = 0.35, outlier.shape = NA) +
848     ggplot2::geom_jitter(ggplot2::aes(shape = LandType), width = 0.10, size = 1.55, alpha = 0.62, stroke = 0.25) +
849     ggplot2::geom_point(data = stats, ggplot2::aes(x = LandType, y = mean), inherit.aes = FALSE, shape = 23, fill = "white", colour = "#222222", size = 2.15, stroke
= 0.42) +
850     ggplot2::geom_text(data = stats, ggplot2::aes(x = LandType, y = label_y, label = Letter), inherit.aes = FALSE, family = "Arial", fontface = "bold", size = 6.5 /
ggplot2::.pt, colour = "#222222") +
851     land_scales(c("colour", "fill", "shape")) +
852     ggplot2::guides(colour = "none", fill = "none", shape = "none") +
853     ggplot2::coord_cartesian(ylim = c(y_pos$bottom, y_pos$top), clip = "off") +
854     ggplot2::labs(title = title, x = NULL, y = y_label) +
855     theme_sci(base_size = 8.1, legend_position = "none")
856   if (annotate_paddy) {
857     fit <- stats::lm(stats::as.formula(paste(variable, "~ PaddyStatus")), data = samples)
858     p_value <- stats::anova(fit)[["Pr(>F)"]][1]
859     pd <- samples[[variable]][samples$PaddyStatus == "Paddy"]
860     np <- samples[[variable]][samples$PaddyStatus == "Non-paddy"]
861     lab <- paste0("Paddy - Non-paddy = ", formatC(mean(pd, na.rm = TRUE) - mean(np, na.rm = TRUE), digits = 1, format = "f"), "\n", format_p(p_value))
862     p <- p + ggplot2::annotate("label", x = 3.18, y = Inf, label = lab, vjust = 1.10, family = "Arial", size = 5.2 / ggplot2::.pt, fill = "white", linewidth = 0.2)
863   }
864   p
865 }
866
867 p_d <- cumulative_panel("CO2_cumulative_g_m2_season", "CO cumulative emission", "CO (g m-2 season-1)")
868 p_e <- cumulative_panel("CH4_cumulative_g_m2_season", "CH cumulative emission", "CH (g m-2 season-1)", annotate_paddy = TRUE)
869
870 temp_flux <- build_temperature_flux_data(samples)
871 trend_colors <- c("CO2 Non-paddy" = "#1F1F1F", "CO2 Paddy" = "#005AB5", "CH4 Non-paddy" = "#666666", "CH4 Paddy" = "#B2182B")
872 trend_types <- c("CO2 Non-paddy" = "solid", "CO2 Paddy" = "longdash", "CH4 Non-paddy" = "dotdash", "CH4 Paddy" = "twodash")
873 trend_labels <- c("CO Non-paddy", "CO Paddy", "CH Non-paddy", "CH Paddy")
874 p_f <- ggplot2::ggplot(temp_flux, ggplot2::aes(x = Temperature, y = Flux_z)) +
875   ggplot2::geom_point(ggplot2::aes(fill = LandType, shape = Gas), colour = "#4C4C4C", size = 1.45, alpha = 0.64, stroke = 0.25) +
876   ggplot2::geom_smooth(ggplot2::aes(colour = TrendGroup, linetype = TrendGroup, group = TrendGroup), method = "lm", formula = y ~ x, se = FALSE, linewidth = 0.9) +
877   ggplot2::scale_fill_manual(name = "LandType", values = LAND_COLORS, drop = FALSE) +
878   ggplot2::scale_shape_manual(name = "Gas", values = c(CO2 = 21, CH4 = 24), labels = c(CO2 = expression(CO[2]), CH4 = expression(CH[4]))) +
879   ggplot2::scale_colour_manual(name = "Trend line", values = trend_colors, labels = trend_labels, drop = FALSE) +
880   ggplot2::scale_linetype_manual(name = "Trend line", values = trend_types, labels = trend_labels, drop = FALSE) +
881   ggplot2::labs(title = "Temperature-GHG relationship", x = "Temperature (°C)", y = "Standardized flux (z-score)") +
882   theme_sci(base_size = 8.1, legend_position = "bottom") +
883   ggplot2::guides(fill = "none")
884
885 final <- ((p_a | p_b | p_c) / (p_d | p_e | p_f)) +
886   patchwork::plot_layout(heights = c(0.88, 1.22), guides = "collect") +
887   patchwork::plot_annotation(tag_levels = "A") &
888   ggplot2::theme(legend.position = "bottom", plot.tag = ggplot2::element_text(family = "Arial", face = "bold", size = 13, colour = "#111111"))
889   save_plot(final, "public_Fig5_greenhouse_gas", 308.0, 198.2)
890 }
891
892 correlation_matrix <- function(data, variables, method = "spearman") {
893   rows <- expand.grid(x = variables, y = variables, stringsAsFactors = FALSE)

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```

894 rows <- tibble::as_tibble(rows) |>
895   dplyr::rowwise() |>
896   dplyr::mutate(
897     result = list(pair_cor(data[[x]], data[[y]], method)),
898     estimate = result$r,
899     p_value = result$p,
900     n = result$n,
901     significance = p_symbol(p_value)
902   ) |>
903   dplyr::ungroup() |>
904   dplyr::select(-result)
905 readr::write_csv(rows, file.path(output_tables, "public_correlation_matrix_spearman.csv"))
906 rows
907 }
908
909 make_fig6_correlation_network <- function(samples) {
910   vars <- c("pH", "EC", "ion_Na_0_20", "ion_CO3_0_20", "ion_HCO3_0_20", "ion_Ca_0_20", "ion_SO4_0_20", "agg_gt2000", "agg_53_250", "MWD", "Temperature_mean", "CO2_mean", "CH4_mean")
911   labels <- c("pH", "EC", "Na+", "CO2-", "HCO-", "Ca2+", "SO2-", ">2000 µm", "53-250 µm", "MWD", "Temperature", "CO2 mean", "CH4 mean")
912   names(labels) <- vars
913   groups <- c(
914     pH = "Salt-alkali", EC = "Salt-alkali",
915     ion_Na_0_20 = "Ions", ion_CO3_0_20 = "Ions", ion_HCO3_0_20 = "Ions", ion_Ca_0_20 = "Ions", ion_SO4_0_20 = "Ions",
916     agg_gt2000 = "Aggregate", agg_53_250 = "Aggregate", MWD = "Aggregate",
917     Temperature_mean = "Temperature", CO2_mean = "Gas", CH4_mean = "Gas"
918   )
919   group_colors <- c("Salt-alkali" = "#D9822B", Ions = "#4C78A8", Aggregate = "#1B9E77", Temperature = "#737373", Gas = "#C76AA6")
920   cm_long <- correlation_matrix(samples, vars, "spearman")
921   heat <- cm_long |>
922     dplyr::mutate(
923       Star = ifelse(x == y, "", significance),
924       X = factor(x, levels = vars, labels = labels),
925       Y = factor(y, levels = rev(vars), labels = rev(labels))
926     )
927
928   p_a <- ggplot2::ggplot(heat, ggplot2::aes(X, Y, fill = estimate)) +
929     ggplot2::geom_tile(colour = "white", linewidth = 0.25) +
930     ggplot2::geom_text(ggplot2::aes(label = ifelse(Star == "ns", "", Star)), family = "Arial", size = 7.5 / ggplot2::.pt) +
931     ggplot2::scale_fill_gradient2(low = "#2166AC", mid = "#F7F7F7", high = "#B2182B", limits = c(-1, 1), name = "Spearman\rho") +
932     ggplot2::labs(title = "Ordered Spearman correlation matrix\n(surface ions: 0-20 cm)", x = NULL, y = NULL) +
933     theme_sci(legend_position = "right") +
934     ggplot2::theme(axis.text.x = ggplot2::element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1), axis.line = ggplot2::element_blank(), panel.grid = ggplot2::element_blank())
935
936   edge_table <- cm_long |>
937     dplyr::filter(match(x, vars) < match(y, vars), abs(estimate) >= 0.50, p_value < 0.05) |>
938     dplyr::rename(from = x, to = y, r = estimate, p = p_value)
939   readr::write_csv(edge_table, file.path(output_tables, "public_correlation_network_edges.csv"))
940   if (!nrow(edge_table)) stop("No correlation network edges met |rho| >= 0.50 and P < 0.05.")
941   graph <- igraph::graph_from_data_frame(edge_table, directed = FALSE, vertices = data.frame(name = vars))
942   manual_xy <- data.frame(
943     name = vars,
944     x = c(-0.15, 0.10, 0.25, 0.55, 0.55, 0.25, 0.10, -1.65, -1.65, -1.95, 1.88, 2.18, 2.18),
945     y = c(0.48, 0.98, 0.18, 0.66, -0.24, -0.76, -1.18, 0.66, -0.56, 0.02, 0.32, -0.16, -0.62)
946   )
947   nodes <- manual_xy
948   nodes$Label <- labels[nodes$name]
949   nodes$Group <- groups[nodes$name]
950   nodes$Degree <- igraph::degree(graph)[nodes$name]
951   label_xy <- data.frame(
952     name = vars,

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```

953   label_x = c(-0.54, -0.18, 0.74, 0.98, 1.10, 0.72, -0.36, -2.20, -2.24, -2.30, 2.25, 2.45, 2.45),
954   label_y = c(0.42, 1.22, 0.07, 0.87, -0.34, -0.78, -1.28, 0.90, -0.88, 0.15, 0.50, -0.06, -0.56)
955   )
956   nodes <- dplyr::left_join(nodes, label_xy, by = "name")
957   edges_plot <- edge_table |>
958     dplyr::left_join(nodes[, c("name", "x", "y")], by = c("from" = "name")) |>
959     dplyr::rename(x = x, y = y) |>
960     dplyr::left_join(nodes[, c("name", "x", "y")], by = c("to" = "name"), suffix = c("", "end")) |>
961     dplyr::mutate(Sign = ifelse(r > 0, "Positive", "Negative"), Strength = cut(abs(r), breaks = c(0.50, 0.70, 0.90, Inf), labels = c("0.50-0.70", "0.70-0.90", ">0.90"
), include.lowest = TRUE, right = FALSE))
962
963   p_b <- ggplot2::ggplot() +
964     ggplot2::geom_segment(data = edges_plot, ggplot2::aes(x, y, xend = xend, yend = yend, colour = Sign, linetype = Sign, linewidth = Strength), alpha = 0.78, lineend
= "round") +
965     ggplot2::geom_point(data = nodes, ggplot2::aes(x, y, fill = Group, size = Degree), shape = 21, colour = "white", stroke = 0.7) +
966     ggplot2::geom_label(data = nodes, ggplot2::aes(label_x, label_y, label = Label), family = "Arial", size = 6.7 / ggplot2::.pt, label.padding = grid::unit(0.08, "li
nes"), label.r = grid::unit(0.05, "lines"), linewidth = 0.12, fill = "white", colour = "#222222") +
967     ggplot2::scale_colour_manual(values = c(Positive = "#B2182B", Negative = "#2166AC")) +
968     ggplot2::scale_linetype_manual(values = c(Positive = "solid", Negative = "dashed")) +
969     ggplot2::scale_fill_manual(values = group_colors) +
970     ggplot2::scale_linewidth_manual(values = c("0.50-0.70" = 0.30, "0.70-0.90" = 0.58, ">0.90" = 0.86), guide = "none") +
971     ggplot2::scale_size_continuous(range = c(3.2, 6.5), guide = "none") +
972     ggplot2::labs(title = "Correlation network") +
973     ggplot2::coord_equal(xlim = c(-2.55, 2.70), ylim = c(-1.45, 1.34), clip = "off") +
974     theme_sci() +
975     ggplot2::guides(colour = "none", linetype = "none", fill = "none") +
976     ggplot2::theme(axis.title = ggplot2::element_blank(), axis.text = ggplot2::element_blank(), axis.ticks = ggplot2::element_blank(), axis.line = ggplot2::element_bla
nk(), panel.grid = ggplot2::element_blank(), legend.position = "none")
977
978   final <- (p_a | p_b) +
979     patchwork::plot_layout(guides = "keep") +
980     patchwork::plot_annotation(tag_levels = "A") &
981     ggplot2::theme(plot.tag = ggplot2::element_text(family = "Arial", face = "bold", size = 12, colour = "#111111"))
982   save_plot(final, "public_fig6_correlation_network", 180, 100)
983 }
984
985 make_fig7_tradeoff <- function(sites) {
986   point_data <- sites |>
987     dplyr::filter(is.finite(restoration_benefit), is.finite(MWD), is.finite(harmful_ion_burden_0_60), is.finite(CH4_cumulative_g_m2_season), is.finite(CO2_cumulative_
g_m2_season))
988
989   scatter_panel <- function(data, x_var, y_var, x_lab, y_lab, title, quadrant = FALSE, show_legend = FALSE) {
990     p <- ggplot2::ggplot(data, ggplot2::aes(x = .data[[x_var]], y = .data[[y_var]]))
991     if (quadrant) {
992       p <- p +
993         ggplot2::geom_vline(xintercept = stats::median(data[[x_var]], na.rm = TRUE), colour = "#777777", linetype = "dashed", linewidth = 0.35) +
994         ggplot2::geom_hline(yintercept = stats::median(data[[y_var]], na.rm = TRUE), colour = "#777777", linetype = "dashed", linewidth = 0.35)
995     }
996     p +
997       ggplot2::geom_smooth(method = "loess", formula = y ~ x, span = 0.9, se = FALSE, colour = "grey45", linewidth = 0.7, na.rm = TRUE) +
998       ggplot2::geom_point(ggplot2::aes(fill = LandType, colour = LandType, shape = PaddyStatus), size = 2.55, stroke = 0.50, alpha = 0.90, na.rm = TRUE) +
999       ggplot2::geom_point(data = data[data$LandType == "OPF", , drop = FALSE], ggplot2::aes(x = .data[[x_var]], y = .data[[y_var]]), inherit.aes = FALSE, shape = 24,
fill = NA, colour = "#8A2E61", size = 3.35, stroke = 0.72, alpha = 0.95) +
1000     ggplot2::scale_fill_manual(name = "LandType", values = LAND_COLORS, drop = FALSE) +
1001     ggplot2::scale_colour_manual(name = "LandType", values = LAND_COLORS, drop = FALSE) +
1002     ggplot2::scale_shape_manual(name = "Paddy status", values = PADDY_SHAPES, drop = FALSE) +
1003     ggplot2::labs(title = title, x = x_lab, y = y_lab) +
1004     ggplot2::guides(colour = "none", fill = if (show_legend) ggplot2::guide_legend(order = 1) else "none", shape = if (show_legend) ggplot2::guide_legend(order = 2)
else "none") +
1005     theme_sci(base_size = 8.1, legend_position = if (show_legend) "bottom" else "none")

```

```

1006 }
1007
1008 x_lab <- "Restoration benefit\n[z(MWD) - z(0-60 cm harmful ion burden)]"
1009 p_a <- scatter_panel(point_data, "restoration_benefit", "CH4_cumulative_g_m2_season", x_lab, "CH emission (g m-2 season-1)", "Restoration benefit and CH emission"
, TRUE, TRUE)
1010 p_b <- scatter_panel(point_data, "MWD", "CH4_cumulative_g_m2_season", "MWD (mm)", "CH emission\n(g m-2 season-1)", "MWD and CH emission")
1011 p_c <- scatter_panel(point_data, "harmful_ion_burden_0_60", "CH4_cumulative_g_m2_season", "0-60 cm harmful ion burden\n(cmolc kg-1 cm)", "CH emission\n(g m-2 seaso
n-1)", "Harmful ion burden and CH emission")
1012 p_d <- scatter_panel(point_data, "restoration_benefit", "CO2_cumulative_g_m2_season", x_lab, "CO emission (g m-2 season-1)", "Restoration benefit and CO emission"
, TRUE)
1013 p_e <- scatter_panel(point_data, "MWD", "CO2_cumulative_g_m2_season", "MWD (mm)", "CO emission\n(g m-2 season-1)", "MWD and CO emission")
1014 p_f <- scatter_panel(point_data, "harmful_ion_burden_0_60", "CO2_cumulative_g_m2_season", "0-60 cm harmful ion burden\n(cmolc kg-1 cm)", "CO emission\n(g m-2 seaso
n-1)", "Harmful ion burden and CO emission")
1015
1016 final <- ((p_a | (p_b / p_c)) / (p_d | (p_e / p_f))) +
1017 patchwork::plot_layout(widths = c(1.75, 1), guides = "collect") +
1018 patchwork::plot_annotation(tag_levels = "A") &
1019 ggplot2::theme(legend.position = "bottom", plot.tag = ggplot2::element_text(family = "Arial", face = "bold", size = 13.5, colour = "#111111"))
1020 save_plot(final, "public_Fig7_restoration_climate_tradeoff", 255, 220)
1021 }
1022
1023 make_figs1_ion_heatmap <- function(samples) {
1024   site_means <- samples |>
1025     dplyr::group_by(LandType, Site_ID) |>
1026     dplyr::summarise(dplyr::across(dplyr::starts_with("ion_"), ~mean(.x, na.rm = TRUE)), .groups = "drop")
1027   long <- dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(DEPTH_SPECS$depth_key, function(depth) {
1028     dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(ION_SPECS$ion_key, function(ion) {
1029       tibble::tibble(
1030         LandType = site_means$LandType,
1031         Site_ID = site_means$Site_ID,
1032         Depth = DEPTH_SPECS$depth_label[DEPTH_SPECS$depth_key == depth],
1033         Ion = ION_LABELS[[ion]],
1034         Value = site_means[[paste("ion", ion, depth, sep = "_")]]
1035       )
1036     })))
1037   |>
1038   dplyr::group_by(Ion) |>
1039   dplyr::mutate(Z = z_score(Value)) |>
1040   dplyr::ungroup() |>
1041   dplyr::mutate(
1042     Site_ID = factor(Site_ID, levels = rev(SITE_LEVELS)),
1043     Ion = factor(Ion, levels = unname(ION_LABELS)),
1044     Depth = factor(Depth, levels = DEPTH_SPECS$depth_label),
1045     LandType = factor(LandType, levels = LAND_LEVELS)
1046   )
1047   p <- ggplot2::ggplot(long, ggplot2::aes(Ion, Site_ID, fill = Z)) +
1048     ggplot2::geom_tile(colour = "white", linewidth = 0.25) +
1049     ggplot2::facet_grid(LandType ~ Depth, scales = "free_y", space = "free_y") +
1050     ggplot2::scale_fill_gradient2(low = "#2166AC", mid = "#F7F7F7", high = "#B2182B", midpoint = 0, name = "Within-ion\nz-score") +
1051     ggplot2::labs(title = "All major ions across three soil layers", x = NULL, y = NULL) +
1052     theme_sci(legend.position = "right") +
1053     ggplot2::theme(axis.text.x = ggplot2::element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1), axis.line = ggplot2::element_blank(), panel.grid = ggplot2::element_blank(), panel.spac
ing = grid::unit(1.5, "pt"))
1054   final <- p + patchwork::plot_annotation(tag_levels = "A") &
1055     ggplot2::theme(plot.tag = ggplot2::element_text(family = "Arial", face = "bold", size = 12))
1056   save_plot(final, "public_FigS1_ion_site_heatmap", 180, 140)
1057 }
1058
1059 make_figs2_pairs <- function(samples) {
1060   plot_data <- samples |>

```

```

1061   dplyr::select(LandType, pH, EC, Na = ion_Na_0_20, CO3 = ion_CO3_0_20, HCO3 = ion_HCO3_0_20, SO4 = ion_SO4_0_20, MWD, CO2_cumulative = CO2_cumulative_g_m2_season,
CH4_cumulative = CH4_cumulative_g_m2_season)
1062   var_keys <- c("pH", "EC", "Na", "CO3", "HCO3", "SO4", "MWD", "CO2_cumulative", "CH4_cumulative")
1063   var_labels <- c(pH = "pH", EC = "EC", Na = "Na+", CO3 = "CO2-", HCO3 = "HCO-", SO4 = "SO2-", MWD = "MWD", CO2_cumulative = "CO2 cumulative", CH4_cumulative = "CH
cumulative")
1064
1065   pair_rows <- dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(seq_along(var_keys), function(i) {
1066     if (i == 1L) return(NULL)
1067     dplyr::bind_rows(lapply(seq_len(i - 1L), function(j) {
1068       pear <- pair_cor(plot_data[[var_keys[j]]], plot_data[[var_keys[i]]], "pearson")
1069       spear <- pair_cor(plot_data[[var_keys[j]]], plot_data[[var_keys[i]]], "spearman")
1070       fit <- stats::lm(plot_data[[var_keys[i]]] ~ plot_data[[var_keys[j]]])
1071       fit_sum <- summary(fit)
1072       tibble::tibble(
1073         x_variable = var_labels[[var_keys[j]]],
1074         y_variable = var_labels[[var_keys[i]]],
1075         pearson_r = pear$r,
1076         pearson_p = pear$p,
1077         spearman_rho = spear$r,
1078         spearman_p = spear$p,
1079         lm_slope = unname(stats::coef(fit)[2]),
1080         lm_intercept = unname(stats::coef(fit)[1]),
1081         lm_p = fit_sum$coefficients[2, 4],
1082         lm_r2 = fit_sum$r.squared,
1083         n = pear$n
1084       )
1085     })))
1086   ))
1087   readr::write_csv(pair_rows, file.path(output_tables, "public_FigS2_pairwise_regression_statistics.csv"))
1088
1089   theme_matrix <- function(base_size = 6.2) {
1090     theme_sci(base_size = base_size, legend_position = "bottom") +
1091     ggplot2::theme(
1092       panel.grid.major = ggplot2::element_line(colour = "#E9E9E9", linewidth = 0.25),
1093       axis.text = ggplot2::element_text(size = base_size - 1.0),
1094       axis.title = ggplot2::element_text(size = base_size),
1095       plot.title = ggplot2::element_text(size = base_size + 0.7, face = "bold", hjust = 0.5),
1096       plot.margin = ggplot2::margin(1.2, 1.2, 1.2, 1.2)
1097     )
1098   }
1099   corr_for <- function(x_key, y_key) {
1100     pc <- pair_cor(plot_data[[x_key]], plot_data[[y_key]], "pearson")
1101     list(label = paste0("r = ", formatC(pc$r, digits = 2, format = "f"), "\n", p_symbol(pc$p)), r = pc$r)
1102   }
1103   make_lower <- function(x_key, y_key, show_x, show_y, show_legend) {
1104     ggplot2::ggplot(plot_data, ggplot2::aes(x = .data[[x_key]], y = .data[[y_key]])) +
1105     ggplot2::geom_smooth(method = "lm", formula = y ~ x, se = TRUE, colour = "#222222", fill = "#D9D9D9", linewidth = 0.42, alpha = 0.35, na.rm = TRUE) +
1106     ggplot2::geom_point(ggplot2::aes(colour = LandType), size = 0.78, alpha = 0.62, stroke = 0, na.rm = TRUE, show.legend = show_legend) +
1107     ggplot2::scale_colour_manual(name = "LandType", values = LAND_COLORS, drop = FALSE) +
1108     ggplot2::guides(colour = if (show_legend) ggplot2::guide_legend(override.aes = list(size = 2.2, alpha = 1)) else "none") +
1109     ggplot2::labs(x = if (show_x) var_labels[[x_key]] else NULL, y = if (show_y) var_labels[[y_key]] else NULL) +
1110     theme_matrix() +
1111     ggplot2::theme(axis.text.x = if (show_x) ggplot2::element_text(size = 4.7) else ggplot2::element_blank(), axis.text.y = if (show_y) ggplot2::element_text(size =
4.7) else ggplot2::element_blank())
1112   }
1113   make_upper <- function(x_key, y_key) {
1114     info <- corr_for(x_key, y_key)
1115     ggplot2::ggplot(data.frame(x = 1, y = 1, r = info$r, label = info$label), ggplot2::aes(x, y, fill = r)) +
1116     ggplot2::geom_tile(colour = "#FFFFFF", linewidth = 0.25) +
1117     ggplot2::geom_text(ggplot2::aes(label = label), family = "Arial", size = 5.3 / ggplot2::.pt, lineheight = 0.92, colour = "#222222") +

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1118 ggplot2::scale_fill_gradient2(low = "#4575B4", mid = "#FFFFFF", high = "#D73027", midpoint = 0, limits = c(-1, 1), na.value = "#F3F3F3", guide = "none") +
1119 ggplot2::coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0.5, 1.5), ylim = c(0.5, 1.5), expand = FALSE) +
1120 theme_matrix() +
1121 ggplot2::theme(axis.title = ggplot2::element_blank(), axis.text = ggplot2::element_blank(), axis.ticks = ggplot2::element_blank(), panel.grid = ggplot2::element
  _blank(), axis.line = ggplot2::element_blank(), plot.margin = ggplot2::margin(0.8, 0.8, 0.8, 0.8))
1122 }
1123 make_diag <- function(key, show_x, show_y) {
1124   ggplot2::ggplot(plot_data, ggplot2::aes(x = .data[[key]])) +
1125     ggplot2::geom_histogram(bins = 9, fill = "#B9C9D8", colour = "#555555", linewidth = 0.25, na.rm = TRUE) +
1126     ggplot2::labs(title = var_labels[[key]], x = if (show_x) var_labels[[key]] else NULL, y = NULL) +
1127     theme_matrix() +
1128     ggplot2::theme(axis.text.x = if (show_x) ggplot2::element_text(size = 4.7) else ggplot2::element_blank(), axis.text.y = if (show_y) ggplot2::element_text(size =
  4.7) else ggplot2::element_blank())
1129 }
1130
1131 cells <- list()
1132 n_vars <- length(var_keys)
1133 for (i in seq_len(n_vars)) {
1134   for (j in seq_len(n_vars)) {
1135     y_key <- var_keys[i]
1136     x_key <- var_keys[j]
1137     cells[[length(cells) + 1L]] <- if (i == j) {
1138       make_diag(x_key, show_x = i == n_vars, show_y = j == 1L)
1139     } else if (i > j) {
1140       make_lower(x_key, y_key, show_x = i == n_vars, show_y = j == 1L, show_legend = i == n_vars && j == 1L)
1141     } else {
1142       make_upper(x_key, y_key)
1143     }
1144   }
1145 }
1146 final <- patchwork::wrap_plots(cells, ncol = n_vars, guides = "collect") &
1147   ggplot2::theme(legend.position = "bottom", plot.background = ggplot2::element_rect(fill = "white", colour = NA))
1148 save_plot(final, "public_FigS2_pairwise_regressions", 260, 260)
1149 }
1150
1151 build_pca_sensitivity <- function(sites) {
1152   pca_vars <- c("MWD", "harmful_ion_burden_0_60", "pH", "EC", "Na_burden_0_60", "CO3_burden_0_60", "HCO3_burden_0_60")
1153   d <- sites |>
1154     dplyr::select(LandType, Site_ID, PaddyStatus, restoration_benefit, CH4_CO2eq_g_m2_season, direct_ghg_cost_g_m2_season, dplyr::all_of(pca_vars)) |>
1155     tidyr::drop_na()
1156   x <- data.frame(
1157     MWD_positive = d$MWD,
1158     harmful_ion_burden_negative = -d$harmful_ion_burden_0_60,
1159     pH_stress_negative = -d$pH,
1160     EC_stress_negative = -d$EC,
1161     Na_negative = -d$Na_burden_0_60,
1162     CO3_negative = -d$CO3_burden_0_60,
1163     HCO3_negative = -d$HCO3_burden_0_60,
1164     check.names = FALSE
1165   )
1166   pca <- stats::prcomp(x, center = TRUE, scale. = TRUE)
1167   pc1 <- pca$x[, 1]
1168   if (stats::cor(pc1, d$restoration_benefit, use = "complete.obs") < 0) pc1 <- -pc1
1169   d$PCA_restoration_index <- as.numeric(pc1)
1170   attr(d, "explained") <- (pca$sdev^2) / sum(pca$sdev^2)
1171   attr(d, "loadings") <- pca$rotation
1172   d
1173 }
1174
1175 make_figs3_pca <- function(sites) {

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1176 d <- build_pca_sensitivity(sites)
1177 explained <- attr(d, "explained")
1178 pc <- pair_cor(d$restoration_benefit, d$PCA_restoration_index, "pearson")
1179 stat_rows <- tibble::tibble(
1180   metric = c("PC1_explained_percent", "Pearson_r_main_vs_PCA", "Pearson_p_main_vs_PCA"),
1181   value = c(explained[1] * 100, pc$r, pc$p)
1182 )
1183 readr::write_csv(stat_rows, file.path(output_tables, "public_FigS3_PCA_sensitivity_statistics.csv"))
1184 readr::write_csv(as.data.frame(attr(d, "loadings")) |> tibble::rownames_to_column("variable"), file.path(output_tables, "public_FigS3_PCA_loadings.csv"))
1185 pc1_lab <- paste0("PCA restoration index (PC1, ", formatC(explained[1] * 100, digits = 1, format = "f"), "%)")
1186 point_scales <- list(
1187   ggplot2::scale_fill_manual(name = "LandType", values = LAND_COLORS, drop = FALSE),
1188   ggplot2::scale_colour_manual(name = "LandType", values = LAND_COLORS, drop = FALSE),
1189   ggplot2::scale_shape_manual(name = "Paddy status", values = PADDY_SHAPES, drop = FALSE)
1190 )
1191 p1 <- ggplot2::ggplot(d, ggplot2::aes(restoration_benefit, PCA_restoration_index)) +
1192   ggplot2::geom_smooth(method = "lm", formula = y ~ x, se = TRUE, colour = "#333333", fill = "#BDBDBD", alpha = 0.18, linewidth = 0.62) +
1193   ggplot2::geom_point(ggplot2::aes(fill = LandType, colour = LandType, shape = PaddyStatus), size = 2.5, stroke = 0.50, alpha = 0.90) +
1194   point_scales +
1195   ggplot2::annotate("label", x = -Inf, y = Inf, hjust = -0.05, vjust = 1.10, label = paste0("Pearson r = ", formatC(pc$r, digits = 3, format = "f"), "\n", format_p(
pc$p)), family = "Arial", size = 6.7 / ggplot2::pt, linewidth = 0.15, fill = "white") +
1196   ggplot2::labs(title = "Main index vs PCA-based index", x = "Restoration benefit = z(MWD) - z(harmful ion burden)", y = pc1_lab) +
1197   theme_sci(base_size = 8.0, legend_position = "bottom")
1198 p2 <- ggplot2::ggplot(d, ggplot2::aes(PCA_restoration_index, CH4_CO2eq_g_m2_season)) +
1199   ggplot2::geom_smooth(ggplot2::aes(linetype = PaddyStatus, group = PaddyStatus), method = "lm", formula = y ~ x, se = TRUE, colour = "#333333", fill = "#BDBDBD", a
lpha = 0.18, linewidth = 0.62) +
1200   ggplot2::geom_point(ggplot2::aes(fill = LandType, colour = LandType, shape = PaddyStatus), size = 2.5, stroke = 0.50, alpha = 0.90) +
1201   point_scales +
1202   ggplot2::scale_linetype_manual(values = PADDY_LINETYPES) +
1203   ggplot2::labs(title = "PCA index vs CH4 CO2-eq", x = pc1_lab, y = "CH4 CO2-eq (g CO2-eq m-2 season-1)") +
1204   theme_sci(base_size = 8.0, legend_position = "none")
1205 p3 <- ggplot2::ggplot(d, ggplot2::aes(PCA_restoration_index, direct_ghg_cost_g_m2_season)) +
1206   ggplot2::geom_smooth(ggplot2::aes(linetype = PaddyStatus, group = PaddyStatus), method = "lm", formula = y ~ x, se = TRUE, colour = "#333333", fill = "#BDBDBD", a
lpha = 0.18, linewidth = 0.62) +
1207   ggplot2::geom_point(ggplot2::aes(fill = LandType, colour = LandType, shape = PaddyStatus), size = 2.5, stroke = 0.50, alpha = 0.90) +
1208   point_scales +
1209   ggplot2::scale_linetype_manual(values = PADDY_LINETYPES) +
1210   ggplot2::labs(title = "PCA index vs direct GHG cost", x = pc1_lab, y = "Direct GHG cost (g CO2-eq m-2 season-1)") +
1211   theme_sci(base_size = 8.0, legend_position = "none")
1212 final <- p1 + p2 + p3 +
1213   patchwork::plot_layout(widths = c(1, 1, 1), guides = "collect") +
1214   patchwork::plot_annotation(tag_levels = "A") &
1215   ggplot2::theme(legend.position = "bottom", plot.tag = ggplot2::element_text(family = "Arial", face = "bold", size = 13, colour = "#111111"))
1216 save_plot(final, "public_FigS3_restoration_index_sensitivity", 240, 82)
1217 }
1218
1219 validate_outputs <- function(paths) {
1220   flat <- unlist(paths, use.names = FALSE)
1221   missing_or_small <- flat[!file.exists(flat) | file.info(flat)$size < 1000]
1222   if (length(missing_or_small)) stop("Missing or too-small output(s): ", paste(missing_or_small, collapse = ", "))
1223   invisible(TRUE)
1224 }
1225
1226 raw_mtime_before <- file.info(raw_xlsx)$mtime
1227 message("Reading: ", raw_xlsx)
1228 samples <- read_project_data()
1229 sites <- site_means_from_samples(samples)
1230 if (nrow(samples) != 80) warning("Expected 80 data rows after cleaning; found ", nrow(samples), ".")
1231 if (nrow(sites) != 16) warning("Expected 16 site means; found ", nrow(sites), ".")
1232

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```
1233 write_core_tables(samples, sites)
1234 stats_outputs <- run_statistical_analyses(samples, sites)
1235
1236 figure_paths <- list(
1237   Fig2 = make_fig2_ph_ec(samples),
1238   Fig3 = make_fig3_ions(samples),
1239   Fig4 = make_fig4_aggregates(samples),
1240   Fig5 = make_fig5_greenhouse_gas(samples),
1241   Fig6 = make_fig6_correlation_network(samples),
1242   Fig7 = make_fig7_tradeoff(sites),
1243   FigS1 = make_figs1_ion_heatmap(samples),
1244   FigS2 = make_figs2_pairs(samples),
1245   FigS3 = make_figs3_pca(sites)
1246 )
1247 validate_outputs(figure_paths)
1248
1249 session_path <- file.path(output_tables, "session_info_public.txt")
1250 utils::capture.output(sessionInfo(), file = session_path)
1251 if (!file.exists(session_path) || file.info(session_path)$size < 100) stop("session_info_public.txt was not written.")
1252
1253 raw_mtime_after <- file.info(raw_xlsx)$mtime
1254 if (!identical(as.numeric(raw_mtime_before), as.numeric(raw_mtime_after))) {
1255   stop("Raw data.xlsx modification time changed during this run.")
1256 }
1257
1258 message("Completed reproducible analysis.")
1259 message("Figures: ", output_figures)
1260 message("Tables: ", output_tables)
```